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Students' Ability To Use English By Introducing Themselves

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Abstrak

Kemampuan berbicara menggunakan bahasa Inggris adalah keterampilan yang sangat berharga. Dengan kemampuan berbicara bahasa Inggris yang baik, seseorang dapat dengan percaya diri memperkenalkan diri nya sendiri maupun orang lain. Tujuan dari penelitian ini mengetahui kemampuan siswa dalam menggunakan bahasa Inggris dan kefasihan saat memperkenalkan diri. Metode yang digunakan penelitian ini menggunakan metode kualitatif dengan desain wawancara dan dokumentasi. Penelitian ini melibatkan 26 siswa dikelas 3 sekolah dasar Al Ittihadiyah. Hasilnya penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa ada beberapa siswa yang fasih dalam menggunakan bahasa Inggris dengan memperkenalkan dirinya, Namun ada juga beberapa siswa yang masih kurang fasih dalam menggunakan bahasa Inggris, kosa kata yang kurang, dan kepercayaan diri yang kurang.

Kata kunci: Kemampuan, Perkenalan, Bahasa Inggris

Abstract

The ability to speak English is a very valuable skill. With good English speaking skills, a person can confidently introduce himself or others. The aim of this research is to determine students' ability to use English and fluency when introducing themselves. The method used in this research uses qualitative methods with interview design and documentation. This research involved 26 students in class 3 of Al Ittihadiyah elementary school. The results of this research show that there are some students who are fluent in using English by introducing themselves. However, there are also some students who are still not fluent in using English, lack vocabulary and lack self-confidence.

Keyword : Ability, Introduction, English

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PENDAHULUAN

According to (Handayani, S., 2016). The need for English language skills in the current period is not something new. Technological advances, increasingly advanced civilization, communication around the world, open up opportunities for anyone to be able to interact in various fields. In this case, the world of education has an important role in supporting the creation of students who are skilled and competitive. One of them is mastering a foreign language, namely English. Entering the time of globalization, every individual is required to be skilled in the field of communication, in this case the use of English which is very necessary for mastering communication technology and for direct interaction. (Ubaedillah, U., Pratiwi, D. I., Mukson, M., Masrikhiyah, R., & Nurpratiwiningsih, L, 2020). English has become an international language that can facilitate its users to communicate with each other without being limited by country differences. This can of course be a positive skill if it can be mastered by students. The earlier and more frequently students learn English, the easier it will be for them to understand it. Then in the future, this ability will become a provision for students to be able to compete nationally and even at the global level.

Every student needs to learn and master English because after they graduate from their education they will be faced with an English interview process if they want to work at a good institution or company. (Afifah, 2012; Mirohi, 2018; Rimadi, 2013; Septiana, 2013). Meanwhile, the education policy conveyed by the deputy Minister of Education and Culture in 2013 states that state elementary schools are not permitted to hold English language lessons. (Yune-lia, 2019) This policy emerged from the results of an evaluation by the Ministry of Education and Culture after a period of 18 years of English language learning activities. This policy also generated a number of protests from

the public, especially parents. Urban communities who have long been familiar with gadgets have certainly been influenced by technological developments. Currently, many instructions on devices are predominantly in English. In other words, English has become a necessity to face the future of every student. Students' need for learning English is considered capable of supporting daily life in developing the field of communication and supporting global learning. Apart from that, according to (Ratmi-ningsih: 2019) the need for English language skills is currently one of the mandatory requirements in obtaining work (Ratmi-ningsih, 2019).

The use of English in education has an important role, especially in the context of globalization and competition in the world of work. English proficiency can impact many aspects, including employment opportunities, access to international educational resources, and the ability to communicate effectively in a global environment. It is important to remember that English proficiency includes not only the ability to speak and write, but also the ability to understand and communicate effectively in academic and professional contexts. In Indonesia, the ability to use English in primary school education has become a major focus in recent years. Improving English language skills at primary school level is expected to provide a strong foundation for students in developing international language skills. This approach is in line with globalization trends and technological developments that enable wider access to information in English. Thus, mastery of English at the primary school level is considered an important first step to equip students with skills that are relevant in the current global context. In addition, the Indonesian government has also encouraged improving English language skills at the primary school level through various policies, including introduction of English language learning programs from an early age. This aims to help students understand and use English more independently and effectively

METHOD

This research uses qualitative research methods by means of interviews. This research was conducted at SD Al-Ittihadiyah Medan Area, Medan, North Sumatra. The subjects of this research were 26 grade 3 students. This research aims to find out how fluent Al-Ittihadiyah elementary school students are in using English, especially when introducing themselves in front of the class or which can be used in public later. The basis for choosing SD Al-Ittihadiyah was because the school was a reference from other students. From the research results, 3rd grade students at SD Al-ittihadiyah took a sample of 8 students. From several samples that have been researched, the results obtained were less than satisfactory, 6 students could not introduce themselves using English, 2 students had fluency in speaking English to introduce themselves himself

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introducing yourself is a very basic activity. You might even do it without realizing it. But when in a forum, you have to include several things that are important to provide personal information. Introduction can be interpreted as an introduction delivered by someone to show their identity. The introduction can be a short introduction or a long introduction, depending on the introductory situation. So that you can make introductions in English well, studying introducing material is very important. Because, introduction is a basis for opening a chat with new people. You also have to be able to introduce yourself properly and correctly when in a formal forum. The main function of the introduction is to introduce yourself. To introduce themselves, students can say their name, age, class, address, and so on.

At the beginning of the lesson, the researcher explained several things including introducing oneself, how to use words, and inviting students to contribute to the lesson. Researchers asked several students to introduce themselves in English to see the extent of their knowledge of the material. There are several learning methods used for the results of this research, including discussion methods and active questioning. In the research, a trial was carried out on grade 3 Al-ittihadiyah elementary school students to introduce themselves using English as many as 26 students, 8 students came forward. It turns out there was a problem with pronunciation. There were 6 students who were not yet fluent in English to introduce themselves, and 2 other students were fluent in introducing themselves using English, both in terms of vocabulary and confidence in introducing themselves in front of the class. From the research conducted, we can conclude that the lack of willingness to speak English among students is due to several factors including: 1. Students who do not pay enough

attention to teachers when teaching English 2. Children's lack of concentration so that it is more likely that if the lesson is explained the child finds it difficult to understand 3. Difficulty in pronunciation basic English vocabulary so that students are afraid of making mistakes in introducing themselves in front of the class.

The introduction material looks simple and easy for many people. However, most of them also often make mistakes in using English in everyday life. At the beginning of learning, quite a few children were enthusiastic about introducing themselves, but after conducting an evaluation by inviting students to be actively involved, very few students were willing to actively contribute. A common mistake in education that often occurs is the teacher's lack of involvement in understanding the students, whether the material that has been delivered is well received by the students, teachers tend to pay less attention to their students due to several factors as well. For this reason, it is important for grade 3 students at al-ittihadiyah elementary school to know the types and practice directly how to make a good and correct introduction. The introductory English material for al-ittihadiyah elementary school children along with examples is not satisfactory. For introduction material in English, of course there is a way to convey these expressions correctly. For this reason, in order for students to be able to convey information or introduce themselves, teachers and parents need more attention to see the development of their child's learning process, and evaluate so that the child does not forget easily and is fluent in using English. If your child's introduction has started to look good, students or people who introduce themselves in public or at school, new people can accept your existence and understand a little about your personality in society.

CONCLUSION

Self-introduction in elementary school is an opportunity for children to learn how to introduce themselves well and correctly. By implementing some introduction etiquette, children can ensure that their introduction is successful and they can make good friends. Some examples of introducing yourself when you first enter school include stating your name, area of origin, hobbies, and other relevant information. Thus, self-introduction in elementary school helps children build positive social relationships. Researchers have conducted research and found results that need to be considered and improved further, both from an overall perspective which is an obstacle for students and teachers, but it does not rule out the possibility that there are also some students who are fluent because it is hoped that English learning will be provided evenly and understood by educators. deeper and together.

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